

In this investigation there is a general lowering of the OH stretch contributed by both the ligands in the 3350 cm^{-1} region. The change in intensity and lowering can be taken as an indication of N-M bond formation and also elimination of the phenolic proton of SAO during complexation.

DAMO exhibits a band around 1655 cm^{-1} due to C = O stretch. This band has disappeared in all the complexes indicating the involvement of carbonyl group in bond formation. The ligand SAO has two bands at 1620 and 1570 cm^{-1} which are due to C = N stretch. The one at 1620 cm^{-1} is slightly shifted to a higher frequency where as the 1570 cm^{-1} band could not be located in the mixed complexes. The band at 1500 cm^{-1} in SAO due to orthosubstituted benzene ring is shifted to a lower frequency and located at 1480 cm^{-1} in all the mixed complexes. The band around 975 cm^{-1} arising out of the N-O stretch of the oxime is located with slight shift in all the mixed complexes.

From an examination of the above data it can be concluded that both the ligands DAMO and SAO are involved in complexation. The oxime protons are intact whereas the proton of the phenolic OH of SAO is eliminated during complexation. General structure assigned to the several lanthanide mixed complexes is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

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Solid State Studies on Polymerization and Depolymerization of Heteropoly Tungstate ion with Fe^{+2} as the Hetero Atom

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A new condensation inorganic polymer, $\text{Na}_6[\text{FeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been prepared and characterised on the basis of analytical and molecular weight determinations. The thermal depolymerization of the product has been studied extensively.

Of condensation of inorganic polymers¹, no reports on 12-heteropoly tungstoferrate are found in the literature. The present note is an attempt towards that line.

To 100 ml. of aqueous solution of M/5 sodium tungstate, 30 ml. of ferrous sulphate was gradually added with constant stirring at a controlled temperature of 80° in a thermostat. After half an hour interval, glacial acetic acid was added dropwise to this solution till pH comes just in the range of 3.5 to 3.7. The solution was boiled constantly for 6 hr., evaporated to half of its volume and allowed to crystallise in vacuo when bright needle shaped crystalline compound came out which was washed with ethanol and recrystallised thrice from hot water. Analysis of the compound was carried out by usual chemical methods and sodium was estimated by flame photometric method. (Found: Na, 3.69; Fe, 1.68; W, 62.09; H, 1.69%. Calcd. for $\text{Na}_6[\text{FeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Na, 3.89; Fe, 1.57; W, 62.22; H, 1.58%). Hydrogen has been analysed by element estimation method.

From the analytical data, the molecular formula of the compound, as per Kegging's view², comes out to be $\text{Na}_6[\text{FeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Molecular weight Determinations: The cryoscopic method, as has been applied successfully by Alexander³ and by Thilo and Krüger⁴ for molecular weight determinations of polymerised silicic acids, condensed phosphates etc., in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate, has also been applied here for the determination of the approximate molecular weight of the compound, in the same condition i.e., in water and in molten sodium sulphate decahydrate^{3,4}. This determination showed the molecular weight of the polymeric compound to be 3495 as compared with the calculated value 3544.11. To know the accurate degree of polymerization this result has been corroborated by X-ray crystal diffraction technique⁵ for molecular weight determinations of heteropoly acids. The crystal diffraction data of the compound are $a = 11.32$, $b = 14.40$, $c = 27.12 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, volume per unit cell $V = 4420.776 \text{ \AA}^3$. Number of molecules per unit cell $Z = 2$. Pycnometric measurement gives the

observed density $\rho_{obs} = 2.6 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation, $\rho_{obs} = \frac{1.66M.z}{V}$, the molecular weight, M , of the compound comes to 3515 against the calculated value 3544.11.

Thermal Depolymerization: The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied on the light of the investigations made by West and Audrieth⁶ and by Babad-Zakhryapin⁷ on a few heteropoly tungstic acids. The apparatus used for this purpose was that described by Ray and Sinha⁸ with continuous pumping the depolymerised product, followed by successive weighing using a thermogravimetric balance and estimations at some stages. The dissociation⁵ of the compound was observed at 75° under reduced pressure when nine molecules of water were eliminated. At 125° further eleven molecules of water were lost. The rest of the eight molecules of water remained intact in the crystal lattice till 220°, above which they were completely removed. This work agreed closely with the work of Scroggie and Clark⁹ with the comparable compounds. When the temperature was raised still higher, then nearly at 350°, the compound was broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of tungsten and iron which has been confirmed by analysis. So the thermal stability of 12-heteropoly tungstoferrate is 350°.

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A Test Paper Method for Detection of Sulphur Dioxide in Low Concentration by a Modified 1 : 10 Phenanthroline Reagent

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1 : 10 phenanthroline has been recommended as a sensitive reagent for the determination of sulphur dioxide by Stephens and Lindstorm¹. The method

is based on the reduction of Fe(III) to Fe(II) by sulphur dioxide and subsequent measurement of coloured complex of Fe(II) and 1 : 10 phenanthroline. The method was modified by Attari *et al.*² by using an acetate buffer. In the present method 1 : 10 phenanthroline is used with zinc acetate and sodium nitroprusside for detection of sulphur dioxide in low concentrations. Hands *et al.* have suggested a test paper impregnated with ammoniacal zinc nitroprusside for detection and determination of sulphur dioxide³. A modification of this method was done by Bourbon *et al.* by using pyridine along with zinc acetate and sodium nitroprusside⁴. The method is further modified by replacing pyridine with 1 : 10 phenanthroline. It is found that the colour obtained by 1 : 10 phenanthroline is more intense. The sensitivity of the reaction is also improved considerably. The test paper impregnated with the reagents, zinc acetate, sodium nitroprusside and 1 : 10 phenanthroline is successfully used for detection of sulphur dioxide in air upto 0.5 ppm.

Experimental

Reagents: (a) 1M zinc acetate dihydrate in 5% v/v glycerol, (b) 1% w/v solution of sodium nitroprusside, (c) 0.2% w/v solution of 1 : 10 phenanthroline in 50% aqueous ethanol.

All reagents used are of Analytical grade.

Preparation of the Test paper: Test papers are prepared by the following method—Take the above three reagents (a), (b), (c) in 10 ml beakers. Dip Whatman No. 1 filter paper strips (1 × 5 cms) in these solutions serially and dry the paper in a temperature controlled oven at 50–60°. These papers which are cream coloured are stable for few days if kept in well-stoppered dark bottles.

Procedure: Insert a test paper, moistened in glycerol water solution, (5% v/v) in a test paper holder and connect it to a source of suction, fitted with a rotameter. Draw one liter of air through the paper at a rate of 200–250 ml per minute. The colour of test paper turns from cream to brick red and this indicates the presence of sulphur dioxide in the sample.

Results and Discussion

By using 1 : 10 phenanthroline, the method becomes more sensitive than the methods reported by Hand⁵ *et al.*, and Bourbon^{3,4}. In aqueous solution the reagent gives a bulky brick red precipitate with sulphur dioxide. The coloured precipitate is sensitive to pH and is insoluble in common organic solvents as benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, acetone, ethanol etc. Attempts are being made to stabilise the coloured precipitate in solution and make a quantitative method for determination of sulphur dioxide, by colorimetric/turbidimetric methods.

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